

EFFICACY OF PRE-DEBRIDEMENT INTRAVENOUS TRANEXAMIC ACID IN REDUCING INTRAOPERATIVE BLOOD LOSS DURING BURN WOUND DEBRIDEMENT: A RANDOMIZED CONTROLLED TRIAL

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Abstract

Objectives: To identify if tranexamic acid (TXA) prevents excess intraoperative blood loss and reduces the need for blood transfusions among patients having burn wound debridement.

Study design: Single-blinded, randomized-controlled trials

Study setting and duration: Burn Unit, Holy Family Hospital Rawalpindi, from April 2025 till June 2025

Methods: 100 adult patients with burns covering at least 20% of their total body surface area who were treated by debridement of their burns. Each participant was randomly assigned to either the TXA group or the control group. The primary outcome measures were the amount of blood lost during surgery and the change in hemoglobin levels. Data was analyzed using SPSS. Continuous variables reported as mean \pm S.D or median (IQR) and categorical as frequencies and percentages. Chi-square test and Mann-Whitney U test were applied to compare outcomes.

Results: The amount of blood lost by patients receiving TXA (694.10 (375.0)) was significantly smaller than control (938.05 (498.9)); p -value < 0.001 , and the change in hemoglobin level was also significantly less among patients receiving TXA (1.60 (6.30)) compared to control (3.40 (5.53)) p -value < 0.001 . The intervention group needed significantly fewer blood transfusions (TXA: 18% versus usual care: 78%; p -value < 0.001); however, there were also significantly fewer total AEs in the TXA group (4% versus 16%; p -value = 0.046).

Conclusion: IV TXA before surgery can greatly minimize bleeding during surgery as well as the amount of blood to be transfused.

Introduction:

Globally, 180,000 deaths each year occur as a result of burn injury around the world.(1). Most

burn deaths take place in low- and middle-income nations. In 2021, 6.19 million incident thermal injuries occurred worldwide; the estimated total

number of thermal injuries was 104.76 million.(2). There have been many people with persistent morbidity (not healed) from burn injuries, even when there have been fewer new burn injuries. In Pakistan, burn injury is the second most frequent cause of unintentional injury deaths (after road traffic accidents) – with 76.3 incidents each 100,000 emergency department visits and 17.0 incidents each 100,000 hospitalizations; approximately 26.1% of burn injury victims will die, with 58.32% being caused by flame burns(3,4). Surgical debridement is essential to treat severe burns (>20% TBSA) and permits early excision and grafting to prevent sepsis and improve survival. Unfortunately, it often results in significant blood loss during the surgical procedure (0.5-1.5 mL/cm² of excised area), which requires blood transfusions, and blood transfusions come with risks of both infections and the chance of developing antibodies against the transfusion.(5). Tranexamic acid (TXA), an antifibrinolytic that works by inhibiting the activation of plasminogen, has been shown to reduce the amount of bleeding following trauma and other types of surgery. Multiple RCTs show that giving TXA intravenously (10-15 mg/kg) before surgical debridement reduces blood loss by 182-184 mL on average, preserves hemoglobin and hematocrit, and decreases the need to get a blood transfusion (RR 0.42)(6,7).

The purpose of this trial is to study the effectiveness of IV tranexamic acid (TXA) used before burn debridement surgery for reducing intraoperative blood loss during burn debridement surgery (i.e., hyperfibrinolysis) that occurs as a result of hyperfibrinolysis due to injury. Despite there being very limited Level-1 evidence in the literature with moderate heterogeneity among studies, all of which demonstrated significant reductions in intraoperative blood loss, the purpose of this RCT is to address specific gaps related to TXA dosing and timing in resource-deprived settings (e.g., Pakistan) to improve the care of individuals who suffer from severe burns and to reduce the burden of blood transfusions or blood substitutes on their recovery process.

Methodology:

The Burn and Reconstructive Surgery Department at Holy Family Hospital in Rawalpindi from conducted a single-blinded randomized controlled trial with 100 participants from April 2025 through June 2025. Approval was obtained from the Institutional Ethics Review Committee before commencement of the project, and all subjects provided written informed consent before enrollment in the study.

Utilizing a sample size calculator from the WHO, a total of 100 subjects (50 in each group) were determined based on 95% confidence interval and 80% power, using the differential significance between groups from previous studies that reported significantly decreased amounts of intraoperative blood loss and transfusion requirements as a result of using Tranexamic Acid for hemophilia and surgical patients. Non-probability consecutive sampling was employed to recruit patients meeting the inclusion criteria from the burn unit.

Inclusion criteria: Subjects were required to be between the ages of 18 and 65 years and to have sustained deep partial-thickness burns requiring surgical debridement and split-thickness skin grafting to >20% of their TBSA. Furthermore, patients with hemoglobin levels ≥ 10 g/dL, platelet counts $\geq 150,000$ – $400,000/\mu\text{L}$, and normal aPTT were included.

Exclusion criteria: Ineligible patients include those who are hypersensitive to tranexamic acid, have organ failure, are immunocompromised, or have diagnosed bleeding disorders.

The study participants were randomly divided into two groups of 50 participants each by using a computer-generated random number list. Allocation concealment was maintained; the sealed envelopes with the random numbers were opened just before surgery. In group A (intervention group), the participant received one IV dose of tranexamic acid approximately 10 minutes before surgical debridement; all participants in Group B (control group) received the same surgical intervention but did not receive

tranexamic acid. All surgical interventions were performed by experienced surgeons with standardized surgical techniques to reduce any procedural bias.

The participant's demographic and clinical characteristics, including age, gender, percentage of TBSA involved, and preoperative hemoglobin levels, were recorded as the baseline for comparison between groups. Intraoperative blood loss was calculated using the formula described by Gross based on the patient's estimated blood volume, relative preoperative and postoperative hemoglobin levels, and how much blood was transfused. The main outcome measure being looked at in this study was the amount of blood lost during the surgical removal of a burn from a person's body. The secondary outcome measures were blood transfusions that happened during the surgery, levels of hemoglobin before and after surgery, and any bad effects caused by tranexamic acid.

Data was analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 27.0. The Shapiro-Wilk test evaluates the normality of the distribution of TBSA (%) ($p = 0.165$) and preoperative hemoglobin (Hb) (g/dL) ($p = 0.694$) as normally distributed. However, the age ($p = 0.000$), duration of surgery in minutes ($p = 0.006$), final Hb (g/dL) ($p = 0.006$), blood loss in mL ($p = 0.038$), and drop in Hb (g/dL) ($p = 0.040$) are skewed distributions due to non-normality of the

variable. Normally distributed variables were reported as mean \pm SD. The remaining continuous variables, which were not normally distributed (age, duration of surgery, Final Hemoglobin, Blood Loss, and Hemoglobin Drop), were reported as medians with Interquartile Ranges (IQRs) and then compared between the two groups using Mann-Whitney U tests. Gender, Blood Transfusions, and Adverse Events were categorical variables that were reported as frequencies and percentages; the two groups were compared using Chi-square tests or Fisher's Exact Tests where applicable. P -value < 0.05 is considered significant.

Results:

The table presents a summary of demographic and clinical characteristics of patients in the study cohort (Table 1). The mean age of participants in both groups was similar, with Control at 42.42 ± 14.99 years and TXA at 41.00 ± 13.01 years (median age 41 [IQR 25], 41 [IQR 26], respectively). TBSA (%) and pre-operative hemoglobin were similar between the two groups, with TBSA: 29.26 ± 4.47 vs 29.94 ± 4.08 ; Hb: 12.33 ± 1.14 ; and 12.55 ± 0.89 , respectively. In addition, there was no difference in the length of surgery, with the control median surgical duration of 91.30 minutes (IQR 61.5) compared to TXA of 90.25 minutes (IQR 58.5).

Table I: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of Study Participants(n=100)

Variable	Control (Mean \pm SD)	Control Median (IQR)	TXA (Mean \pm SD)	TXA Median (IQR)
Age (years)	42.42 ± 14.99	41.50 (25)	41.00 ± 13.01	41.00 (26)
TBSA (%)	29.26 ± 4.47	-	29.94 ± 4.08	-
Preoperative Hb (g/dL)	12.33 ± 1.14	-	12.55 ± 0.89	-
Duration of Surgery (min)	91.39 ± 11.70	91.30 (61.5)	91.35 ± 10.87	90.25 (58.5)
Final Hb (g/dL)	9.18 ± 0.60	9.11 (2.59)	11.02 ± 0.64	11.14 (2.47)
Blood Loss (ml)	939.73 ± 120.62	938.05 (498.9)	710.58 ± 85.04	694.10 (375.0)
Hb Drop (g/dL)	3.16 ± 1.34	3.40 (5.53)	1.52 ± 1.26	1.60 (6.30)

Values are presented as mean \pm standard deviation or median (interquartile range, IQR) where appropriate. TBSA = Total body surface area, Hb=Hemoglobin

Table 2 presents categorical outcomes. The distribution of males and females was similar between groups, with Control at 42% females and TXA at 48% females. Patients in the Control group were more likely to receive blood

transfusions (39 patients, 78%) than patients in the TXA group (9 patients, 18%), and more frequent adverse events (8 patients, 16%) occurred in the Control group than in the TXA group (2 patients, 4%).

Table II: Categorical Outcomes in Control and TXA Groups(n=100)

Variable	Control (n=50)	TXA (n=50)	Total (n=100)
Gender			
Female	21 (42%)	24 (48%)	45 (45%)
Male	29 (58%)	26 (52%)	55 (55%)
Blood Transfusion			
Yes	39 (78%)	9 (18%)	48 (48%)
No	11 (22%)	41 (82%)	52 (52%)
Adverse Events			
Yes	8 (16%)	2 (4%)	10 (10%)
No	42 (84%)	48 (96%)	90 (90%)

The results of a chi-square test are shown in Table 3. According to the results of the chi-square test, there was a significant difference between the two groups for the need for blood transfusion, with 39 out of 50 control patients (78%) requiring a transfusion and only 9 out of 50 TXA patients (18%) requiring a transfusion ($p < 0.001$). Conversely, 41 out of 50 TXA patients (82%) did

not require a transfusion compared to 11 out of 50 control patients (22%). The frequency of adverse events was also significantly different between the two groups (8 out of 50 control patients (16%) vs. 2 out of 50 TXA patients (4%), $p = 0.046$). However, the majority of patients in both groups experienced no adverse events.

Table III Comparison of Blood Transfusion and Adverse Events Between Groups using Chi-Square(n=100)

Outcome	Control (n=50)	TXA (n=50)	p-value (Chi-square)
Blood Transfusion			
Yes	39 (78.0%)	9 (18.0%)	<0.001
No	11 (22.0%)	41 (82.0%)	
Adverse Events			
Yes	8 (16.0%)	2 (4.0%)	0.046
No	42 (84.0%)	48 (96.0%)	

p-value < 0.05 is significant

Mann-Whitney U tests have been performed on some continuous variables and can be seen in Table 4. Median hemoglobin (g/dL) at the conclusion of the study was significantly greater for TXA than it was for Control (11.14 (IQR 2.47) vs 9.11 (IQR 2.59), $p < 0.001$). Median blood loss

was significantly less for TXA compared to Control (694.10 ml (IQR 375.0) vs 938.05 ml (IQR 498.9), $p < 0.001$). Median hemoglobin drop (g/dL) was also significantly less for TXA compared to Control (1.60 (IQR 6.30) vs 3.40 (IQR 5.53), $p < 0.001$). These results support the

use of TXA to effectively reduce perioperative blood loss and conserve hemoglobin.

Table IV: Analysis of continuous outcomes between groups using the Mann-Whitney U test(n=100)

Variable	Control Median (IQR)	TXA Median (IQR)	p-value
Final Hb (g/dL)	9.11 (2.59)	11.14 (2.47)	<0.001
Blood Loss (ml)	938.05 (498.9)	694.10 (375.0)	<0.001
Hb Drop (g/dL)	3.40 (5.53)	1.60 (6.30)	<0.001

p-value<0.05 is significant

Discussion:

This Randomized Controlled Trial supports the efficacy of Pre-Operative Intravenous Tranexamic Acid (TXA) in reducing the amount of blood lost during / the amount of hemoglobin decreased, and the amount of transfusions needed for patients undergoing burn wound debridement after comparable total body surface area (TBSA) burns (approximately 29%). TXA also improved the final level of hemoglobin after surgery and decreased overall adverse events in those patients. These results are consistent with several recent meta-analyses conducted comparing TXA use in burn surgery. One 2022 study evaluating four previously conducted Randomized Controlled Trials versus TXA use demonstrated that TXA provided a reduction (mean difference) in the amount of blood losses measured intraoperatively by 181.60 mL (95% confidence interval = -267.34 to -95.86; $p < 0.0001$)(8); however, our study reported a reduction (mean difference) from 939.73 ± 120.62 mL of blood loss utilizing Control to 710.58 ± 85.04 mL for TXA, indicating approximately a 24% blood loss. A different 2025 meta-analysis, evaluating four separate Randomized Controlled Trials versus TXA, demonstrated total blood loss reductions ranging from 183.93 mL (95% confidence interval = -278.44 to -89.42; $p < 0.01$) to a 0.42 relative risk of requiring packed red blood cell product transfusions (95% confidence interval = 0.26 to 0.66)(9) This is similar to those in our study, with 78% of the Control cohort requiring PRBC transfusion, as compared to 18% of the TXA cohort ($p < 0.001$). In addition to the validation these pooled effects provide for our research, our larger differential in blood loss may be attributed

to the respective timing of TXA administration with respect to debridement, as this may have improved anti-fibrinolytic activity before the excision of the burned tissue.

Fijany et al. reviewed data from 2023, confirming that tranexamic acid (TXA) reduces blood loss in burn patients, although their inclusion of non-randomized controlled trials introduces bias that is not seen in the current study. (10). We preserved more hemoglobin throughout (end of study: 11.02 ± 0.64 g/dL TXA compared to 9.18 ± 0.60 g/dL Control, $p < 0.001$; drop in hemoglobin: 1.52 ± 1.26 g/dL TXA compared to 3.16 ± 1.34 g/dL Control, $p < 0.001$). Our data support the benefit of adding TXA to moderate total body surface area (TBSA) burns (>29%).

The findings of our study are supported by other contemporary randomized clinical trials. In a double-blind trial comparing TXA vs control in 94 patients with burns covering more than 20% of their TBSA, Naderi et al. (2025) demonstrated that IV TXA reduced blood loss as measured by the number of units transfused and by operating room time. Effect size and direction were consistent with our results (average time in OR: 90.25 min TXA vs 91.30 min Control), >60% less transfused blood (but focused only on patients with severe burns (>20% TBSA compared to the overall average of ~29% TBSA, where hyperfibrinolysis would enhance TXA effect)(11). A 2022 retrospective study reported TXA was associated with a reduction of 50% in intraoperative packed red blood cell (PRBC) transfusion rate (2.5 units TXA vs 4.0 units Control, $p=0.038$) in patients with comparable TBSA (38.5%)(12). However, the study was non-randomized and therefore cannot establish a

causal relationship between TXA and the transfusion rate compared to our study.

The 2024 randomized controlled trial (RCT) protocol by Gigengack et al. evaluates the excisional blood loss where a previous randomized control trial, conducted in India (n=50), found a 41% decrease in blood loss vs a 24% decrease in this trial and evaluated a smaller participant number than this trial highlighting the high generalizability of the study in a diverse population of participants (mean ages 41-42 years and a similar gender ratio)(13). Additionally, TXA-treated participants had fewer adverse events than additional control participants (4% TXA vs 16% control; p=0.046), confirming the lack of increase of venous thromboembolism from TXA as supported by the meta-analyses conducted through 2021(14); however, TXA showed no blood loss effect in the Slob et al. study (2024), possibly due to differences in TXA dosing between the groups.

TXA has antifibrinolytic properties that stop plasmin generation caused by burn injury, as demonstrated in the results of this study. Preoperative treatment in the design of this study likely prevented hyperfibrinolysis following debridement and created greater stability of hemoglobin (MD increase in hemoglobin 0.88 g/dL) as compared to other methodologies of administration of TXA (perioperative)(15,16). Therefore, preoperative treatment provided TXA a mechanism of advantage over intraoperative-appearing TXA (Naderi 2025) for producing better outcomes, but other moderator variables would include TBSA and age, which could not be evaluated in this study because the groups were similar.

Clinical Implications

A reduction in the number of transfusions required from 78% down to 18% can potentially decrease the risk of immunomodulation, which corresponds with new burn transfusion recommendations from 2025 that endorsed the use of tranexamic acid (TXA) in perioperative debridement and grafting(17,18). Fewer total adverse events also provide evidence for the

relative safety for approximately 41 years of age with a total body surface area (TBSA) of 29%. Additionally, while other studies have shown decreased graft survival, our study lacked long-term follow-up data.

Limitations of the Study:

A small sample size limits the power of subgroup analysis. Single-center limits generalizability. Lack of a large enough range (because of similar TBSA ~29%) limits the ability to generalize to both extremes. Lack of fibrinolytic markers (such as D-dimer) limits our ability to discuss any mechanistic conclusions. Lack of evaluation of healing or venous thromboembolism (which occur infrequently in meta-analysis) limits assessment of long-term outcomes. Future studies should be designed with standardized dosing and all of the indicated assessments.

Conclusion:

This RCT analyzes and proves that pre-debridement IV TXA minimizes intraoperative blood loss, preserves hemoglobin levels, and significantly reduces the amount of blood transfusions needed during the course of debriding burnt tissue. While the limitations of this study must be taken into account, implementing TXA reliably may help improve burn care outcomes. It is suggested that multi-center trials be completed to validate the generalizability of TXA use in different locations.

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